

Metal complexes of unsaturated β -ketoanilides

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Abstract : A new series of β -ketoanilides, in which the keto group attached to olefinic linkage have been synthesized by the reaction of acetoacetanilide and aromatic aldehydes under specified conditions. The existence of these β -ketoanilides predominantly in the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded enol form has been well demonstrated from their IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data. Details on the formation of [ML₂] complexes of these unsaturated β -ketoanilides with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} and their nature of bonding are discussed on the basis of analytical, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data.

Keywords : β -Ketoanilides, metal complexes, IR spectra, mass spectra.

Extensive literature is available on the synthesis, structural characterization and applications of metal complexes of β -ketoanilides such as acetoacetanilides, in which the carbonyl groups are directly attached to alkyl/aryl functions¹⁻⁵. In recent years a number of β -dicarbonyl compounds in which the carbonyl function(s) bonded to olefinic linkage(s) have gained considerable importance⁶ mainly because of the fact that such compounds are structurally related to the active chemical constituents of several traditional medicinal plants. For instance, curcuminoids, the active chemical components present in the Indian medicinal plant turmeric (*Curcuma longa*, Linn, *Zingiberaceae* family) contain three β -dicarbonyl compounds in which the diketone function is directly linked to -CH=CH- groups⁷. Such

'unsaturated' β -dicarbonyl compounds and their metal complexes possess interesting biochemical properties such as antitumour, antioxidant, antifungal and antimicrobial activities⁶⁻⁹. In this paper we report the synthesis and characterization of a new series of β -ketoanilides in which the keto function is directly bonded to a -CH=CH- group and their typical metal complexes.

Results and discussion

Unsaturated β -diketones such as naturally occurring curcuminoids are generally synthesized by Claisen type condensation of aromatic aldehydes with β -diketones containing at least one acetyl group like acetylacetone, benzoylacetone, etc. The reaction is usually carried out in

Table 1. Analytical, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides

Compd. Empirical formula	M.p. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			¹ H NMR (δ , ppm)				Mass spectral data (m/z)
			Found (Calcd.)		N	Enolic OH	NH	Methine	CH ₂	
HL ¹ C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NO ₂	98	68	75.48 (76.98)	5.58 (5.67)	5.37 (5.28)	12.168	9.203	5.997	3.684	265, 188, 173, 162, 145, 134, 131, 120, 103, 102
HL ² C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₂	70	72	79.94 (80.00)	5.36 (5.40)	4.44 (4.44)	12.354	9.504	5.870	3.634	316, 238, 223, 195, 181, 162, 153, 152, 134, 127, 120
HL ³ C ₁₅ H ₁₃ NO ₃	88	65	69.76 (70.60)	5.04 (5.10)	5.36 (5.49)	12.358	9.163	5.870	3.634	255, 178, 163, 162, 135, 134, 121, 120
HL ⁴ C ₁₇ H ₁₅ NO ₃	64	74	72.35 (72.59)	5.50 (5.34)	5.02 (4.98)	13.123	9.787	5.928	3.684	281, 204, 189, 162, 161, 147, 134, 120, 119
HL ⁵ C ₂₁ H ₁₇ NO ₃	72	78	76.48 (76.13)	5.04 (5.14)	4.32 (4.23)	13.258	9.318	5.928	3.568	331, 254, 239, 211, 197, 169, 162, 143, 142, 134, 120

Table 2. Physical and analytical data of the metal complexes of unsaturated β -ketoanilides

Complex	M.p. ($^{\circ}$ C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) :			
			Found (Calcd.)			
			C	H	N	M
[NiL ¹ ₂]	160	76	69.33	4.62	4.74	9.94
C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ NiO ₄			(69.54)	(4.77)	(4.77)	(10.01)
[NiL ² ₂]	210	70	72.88	4.69	4.17	8.56
C ₄₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ NiO ₄			(73.39)	(4.66)	(4.08)	(8.55)
[NiL ² ₂]	138	74	63.04	4.12	4.64	10.28
C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ NiO ₆			(63.52)	(4.23)	(4.94)	(10.36)
[NiL ² ₂]	180	68	65.93	4.56	4.50	9.56
C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ NiO ₆			(65.94)	(4.53)	(4.53)	(9.49)
[NiL ² ₂]	198	72	69.98	4.41	3.87	8.22
C ₄₂ H ₃₂ NiN ₂ O ₆			(70.13)	(4.45)	(3.90)	(8.17)
[CuL ¹ ₂]	176	62	67.94	4.70	4.71	10.64
C ₃₄ H ₂₈ CuN ₂ O ₄			(68.97)	(4.73)	(4.73)	(10.74)
[CuL ² ₂]	160	68	72.18	4.59	3.99	9.01
C ₄₂ H ₃₂ CuN ₂ O ₄			(72.88)	(4.63)	(4.05)	(9.19)
[CuL ³ ₂]	194	72	62.88	4.10	4.88	10.94
C ₃₀ H ₂₄ CuN ₂ O ₆			(62.98)	(4.20)	(4.90)	(11.12)
[CuL ⁴ ₂]	198	70	65.38	4.46	4.44	10.08
C ₃₄ H ₃₂ CuN ₂ O ₆			(65.43)	(4.49)	(4.49)	(10.19)
[CuL ⁵ ₂]	172	75	69.69	4.31	3.86	8.70
C ₄₂ H ₃₂ CuN ₂ O ₆			(69.66)	(4.42)	(3.87)	(8.78)
[ZnL ¹ ₂]	150	76	68.71	4.70	4.68	11.14
C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₄ Zn			(68.76)	(4.72)	(4.72)	(11.02)
[ZnL ² ₂]	142	72	72.14	4.58	4.01	9.30
C ₄₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₄ Zn			(72.69)	(4.62)	(4.04)	(9.33)
[ZnL ³ ₂]	154	70	62.53	4.17	4.86	11.02
C ₃₀ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₆ Zn			(62.79)	(4.19)	(4.88)	(11.40)
[ZnL ⁴ ₂]	162	66	64.34	4.46	4.44	10.21
C ₃₄ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₆ Zn			(65.24)	(4.48)	(4.48)	(10.45)
[ZnL ⁵ ₂]	146	70	69.44	4.32	3.81	8.90
C ₄₂ H ₃₂ N ₂ O ₆ Zn			(69.48)	(4.41)	(3.86)	(9.01)

L = Deprotonated ligand.

Scheme 1

presence of boric oxide and tri(*sec*-butyl)borate in order to prevent the more facile Knoevenagel type condensation⁷. However with acetoacetanilide the reaction product contained more than one compound. Separation of the mixture on a silica gel column using chloroform-acetone (3 : 5 v/v) yielded two compounds. On the basis of elemental analysis, IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral data, the compounds were identified as an unsaturated β -ketoanilide **1** and a diketoanilide **2** (Scheme 1). The unsaturated β -ketoanilide, the major product (~70%) formed stable complexes with Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} ions. The elemental analytical data of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides synthesized from various aromatic aldehydes are given in Table 1. The analytical data (Table 2) together with non-electrolytic nature in DMF

(specific conductance $< 10 \Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$; 10^{-3} M solution) suggest $[\text{ML}_2]$ stoichiometry of the complexes. The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic while Cu^{II} complexes showed normal paramagnetic moment. The observed electronic, IR, ^1H NMR and mass spectra are fully consistent with the structure **3** of the complexes.

Infrared spectra : Acetoacetanilide exists predominantly in the keto form with very small percentage of the enol content². Thus its IR spectrum is characterized by the presence of two strong bands at $\sim 1720 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1667 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to acetyl and the amide carbonyls respectively. The spectra of all the unsaturated β -ketoanilides show two intense bands at $\sim 1670 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 3) assignable respectively to the stretching of the amide carbonyl and to partially enolised cinnamoyl carbonyl function¹⁰. The broad band in the region $2800\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggests the existence of the compounds predominantly in the enolic form¹¹. The spectra of all the compounds showed a prominent band at $\sim 970 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ typical of *trans* -CH=CH-group¹¹.

Spectra of all the complexes in the $1600\text{--}1800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region showed an intense and slightly broadened band at $\sim 1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Table 4). In acetoacetanilide complexes both the acetyl and amide carbonyls show appreciable decrease in frequencies up on complexation². Therefore by considering the position and broadened nature it can be presumed that the band at $\sim 1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to metal bonded dicarbonyl function. The broad band in the region $2800\text{--}3500 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ cleared up in the spectra of metal complexes indicating the replacement of enolic proton by the metal cation during complexation. That the carbonyl groups are involved in bonding with the metal ion as in structure **3** is fur-

ther supported by the appearance of two medium intensity bands at $\sim 420 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 450 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ ¹⁰ (Table 4).

Table 3. Characteristic IR stretching bands (cm^{-1}) of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides

Compounds					Probable assignments
HL ¹	HL ²	HL ³	HL ⁴	HL ⁵	
1670	1666	1678	1677	1672	(C=O) amide
1638	1640	1642	1632	1640	(C=O) chelated
1580	1590	1597	1596	1596	} (C=C) phenyl/ (C=C) alkenyl/ amide II
1545	1542	1573	1564	1574	
1528	1536	1546	1536	1542	
1525	1518	1512	1513	1512	
1240	1232	1238	1214	1244	amide III
967	969	970	976	978	CH=CH <i>trans</i>
690	693	694	692	690	amide V
656	655	660	658	659	amide IV
610	608	617	610	618	amide VI
3326	3272	3239	3238	3114	} OH/NH
2936	2978	3039	2904	3014	

^1H NMR spectra : The ^1H NMR spectra of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides show two one proton signals at $\sim \delta$ 9.5 ppm (broad) and at $\sim \delta$ 12.5 ppm (Table 1) assignable respectively to the NH and enol protons^{12,13} of structure **1**. The olefinic and methylene proton signals appeared at $\sim \delta$ 8 ppm (2H) and $\sim \delta$ 4 ppm (1H). The aryl proton signals are observed in the range δ 6.8–7.5 ppm. The spectra of HL⁴ and HL⁵ displayed signals at δ 10.047 ppm and δ 10.814 ppm due to the phenolic OH groups.

The most characteristic feature of the ^1H NMR spectra

Table 4. Characteristic IR stretching frequencies (cm^{-1}) and mass spectral data of Cu^{II} complexes of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides

Complex	IR bands (cm^{-1})					M-O	Mass spectral data (m/z)
	(C=O)	(C=C) aryl	(C=C) alkenyl	(C-C-C) chelate ring	(CH=CH) <i>trans</i>		
$[\text{CuL}_2]$ $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{28}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_4$	1630s	1558s 1586s	1540m	1520m	968m	418m 470m	593, 591, 516, 514, 501, 499, 439, 437, 409, 407, 490, 488, 387, 385, 330, 265, 203, 201, 173, 162, 120
$[\text{CuL}_2]$ $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{32}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_4$	1626s	1560s 1582s	1549m	1521m	970m	416m 474m	693, 691, 616, 614, 601, 599, 539, 537, 509, 507, 490, 488, 387, 385, 380, 315, 238, 203, 201, 181, 152
$[\text{CuL}_3]$ $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{24}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_6$	1625s	1562s 1584s	1550m	1526m	971m	418m 470m	573, 571, 496, 494, 490, 488, 481, 479, 419, 417, 389, 387, 385, 320, 255, 281, 203, 201, 178, 135, 120
$[\text{CuL}_4]$ $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{28}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_6$	1631s	1564s 1580s	1545m	1522m	975m	416m 485m	625, 623, 548, 546, 533, 531, 471, 469, 441, 439, 490, 488, 387, 385, 346, 281, 203, 201, 189, 162, 120
$[\text{CuL}_5]$ $\text{C}_{42}\text{H}_{32}\text{CuN}_2\text{O}_6$	1622s	1562s 1588s	1546m	1520m	974m	416m 487m	725, 723, 648, 646, 633, 631, 571, 569, 541, 539, 490, 488, 396, 387, 385, 331, 211, 203, 201, 162, 134

L = Deprotonated ligand.

of the diamagnetic Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes is the absence of the low field enol proton signal of the ligands. The NH proton signal remained almost unaffected. This strongly supports that only the enol proton has been replaced by the metal ion and the amide nitrogen is excluded from coordination. The methylene proton signal shifted appreciably to low field compared to the shift in the olefinic protons. This may be due to the aromatic character that might have been imparted to the $\text{C}_3\text{O}_2\text{M}$ ring system of the chelates by the highly conjugated groups attached to the dicarbonyl moiety. The integrated intensities of various signals agree well with the $[\text{ML}_2]$ stoichiometry of the complexes. That the phenolic OH group of HL^4 and HL^5 are not involved in bonding with the metal ion is clearly indicated¹⁴ in the spectra of their Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes.

Mass spectra : Mass spectra of all the unsaturated β -ketoanilides showed intense molecular ion peak, $\text{P}^+ / (\text{P} + 1)^+$ thereby confirming the formulation of the compounds¹⁵. Peaks due to $(\text{Ar}-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{CO})^+$, $(\text{P}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)^+$, $(\text{P}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH})^+$, $(\text{P}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NHCO})^+$, $(\text{P}-\text{ArC}_2\text{H}_2)^+$, etc. are characteristic of all the spectra (Table 1). The FAB mass spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes showed molecular ion peaks corresponding to $[\text{CuL}_2]$ stoichiometry of the complexes. Peaks correspond to $[\text{CuL}]^+$, L^+ , fragments of L^+ are also present in the spectra. The spectra of all the chelates contain a number of fragments containing copper in the 3 : 1 natural abundance of ^{63}Cu and ^{65}Cu isotopes (Table 4).

Table 5. ESR parameters of some Cu^{II} complexes in DMF at 77 K

Cu^{II} complexes of	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	$A_{\parallel} \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$	$A_{\perp} \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}^{-1}$
HL^1	2.268	2.051	156	45.5
HL^2	2.260	2.058	161	44.2

ESR spectra : The ESR spectra of the copper(II) complexes of HL^1 and HL^2 were recorded at 77 K in DMF solution. The observed g and A values (Table 5) are comparable to that reported for copper acetoacetanilide^{16,17}. This suggests the presence of appreciable delocalisation in the chelate ring.

Electronic spectra : The UV spectra of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides show two broad bands with maxima at ~ 380 nm and ~ 260 nm due to the various $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. In complexes these absorption maxima shifted appreciably to low wave numbers. The Cu^{II} complexes showed a broad visible band, λ_{max} at $\sim 15000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. This, together with the measured μ_{eff} values (~ 1.72 B.M.) suggests the square-planar geometry¹⁸. In agreement with this, spectra recorded in pyridine, a broad band centered at $\sim 11000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ was observed which indicates the formation of octahedral pyridine adducts. The observed diamagnetism and

broad medium-intensity band at $\sim 17600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of the Ni^{II} chelates suggest their square-planar geometry. In conformity, the spectra of the chelates in pyridine solution (10^{-3} M) showed three bands corresponding to configurational change to octahedral due to the association of pyridine. The three well-separated absorption bands at λ_{max} ~ 8142 , ~ 13340 and $\sim 24456 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to the transitions; ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}$, ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ respectively.

Antifungal studies : Various biological activities exhibited by unsaturated β -dicarbonyl compounds such as curcuminoids have been the subject of numerous physiological and clinical studies^{6,9}. In the present study antifungal activity of the unsaturated β -ketoanilides and their metal complexes were carried out. The compounds containing -OH group in the aromatic ring (HL^4 and HL^5) showed maximum activity against all tested organisms. The metal complexes studied did not show any significant activity against any of the tested microbes and this may probably be due to the unavailability of the free 1,3-dicarbonyl function for significant interaction with the metal ions present in the cell fluids of the microorganisms.

Experimental

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen percentages were determined by micro analyses (Heraeus Elemental analyzer) at CDRI, Lucknow and metal contents of complexes by AAS (Perkin-Elmer 2380). The electronic spectra of the compounds were recorded on a 1601 Shimadzu UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The IR spectra were recorded using KBr discs on a 8101 Shimadzu FTIR spectrophotometer. The ${}^1\text{H}$ NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 or $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ on a Varian 300 NMR spectrometer. The ESR spectra (X-band) of the copper complexes were recorded at 77 K using a Varian E 112 ESR spectrometer. Mass spectra were recorded on a Jeol/SX-102 mass spectrometer (FAB using Argon and *meta*-nitrobenzyl alcohol as the matrix). Molar conductance of the complexes was determined in DMF at $28 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ using solution of about 10^{-3} M concentration. Magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on a Guoy type magnetic balance.

Synthesis of unsaturated β -ketoanilides : The unsaturated β -ketoanilides were synthesised by the reaction of aromatic aldehydes with acetoacetanilide in presence of boric oxide and tri(*sec*-butyl)borate using *n*-butylamine as the condensing agent. The aldehydes used for condensation reaction were benzaldehyde, naphthalene-1-carbaldehyde, furfural, 2-hydroxybenzaldehyde and 2-hydroxynaphthalene-1-carbaldehyde. A typical procedure for the synthesis is given below.

Acetoacetanilide (1.77 g, 0.01 mol) and boric oxide (0.35 g, 0.005 mol) were mixed and made into a paste with dry ethylacetate and stirred for about 1 h at room temperature. To this, a solution of aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mol) and tri(*sec*-butyl)borate (4.6 g, 0.02 mol) dissolved in dry ethylacetate (~15 mL) was added and stirred for ~5 h with the slow addition of *n*-butylamine (0.5 mL in 5 mL dry ethylacetate) and the reaction mixture was kept overnight. Hot (~70 °C) HCl (0.4 M, 7.5 mL) was added and again stirred for ~1 h. The mixture was extracted repeatedly with ethylacetate and the combined extracts were evaporated to dryness on a water bath to get a pasty mass. To this 10 mL of 2 M HCl was added and kept for ~24 h. The precipitate formed was filtered. The tlc of the products revealed the presence of two compounds and were quantitatively separated by column chromatography as outlined below.

The crude product was dissolved in minimum quantity of dry ethylacetate and placed over a column (2 × 100 cm) densely packed with silica gel (mesh 60–120) and eluted with 3 : 5 v/v chloroform-acetone mixture at a uniform flow rate of 2 mL per min. As the elution proceeds, two bands were developed in the column, a pale yellow lower band and an orange red upper band. The lower region was collected as 10 mL aliquots in separate tubes and in each case the purity was established by tlc. The combined eluates on evaporation gave the pure unsaturated β -ketoanilide 1. The upper region on evaporation gave the pure unsaturated diketoanilide 2.

Synthesis of metal complexes : To a refluxing solution of the β -ketoanilide in ethanol (0.002 mol, 20 mL) an aqueous solution of the metal(II) acetate (0.001 mol, 15 mL) was added drop by drop with stirring. The pH of the solution was adjusted around 6 using sodium acetate and refluxing was continued for ~4 h. The solution was concentrated to half the volume and then cooled in ice. The precipitated complex was filtered, washed several times with water, then with ethanol, recrystallised from hot methanol, and dried in vacuum.

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